

Nordic Urban Archaeology

– Experiences and New Directions

Edited by Kirstine Haase, Hanna Dahlström,
Georg Haggrén, Joakim Kjellberg & Chris McLees.

MUSEUM
ODENSE

NUA

Some questions about bulk finds and the discovery of a shipyard site. A glimpse of Sigüna's maritime Middle Ages

By *Rune Edberg*

ORCID 0009-0001-4070-5115

A translated and slightly edited version of an article in Swedish: **“Några frågor till ett massmaterial och upptäckten av en varvsplats. En glimt av Sigünas maritima medeltid”**.

Published in: Nordic Urban Archaeology – Experiences and New Directions. Edited by Kirstine Haase, Hanna Dahlström, Georg Haggrén, Joakim Kjellberg & Chris McLees. Odense 2025. (Conference proceedings from the first meeting in Network of Urban Archaeology – NUA23 – at Copenhagen City Hall 10–12 May 2023.)

[RE 2026-01-18] • A translated and slightly edited version of an article in Swedish:

Några frågor till ett massmaterial och upptäckten av en varvsplats. En glimt av Sigtunas maritima medeltid.

Published in: *Nordic Urban Archaeology – Experiences and New Directions*. Edited by Kirstine Haase, Hanna Dahlström, Georg Haggrén, Joakim Kjellberg & Chris McLees. Odense 2025. (Conference proceedings from the first meeting in Network of Urban Archaeology – NUA23 – at Copenhagen City Hall 10–12 May 2023.)

Some questions about bulk finds and the discovery of a shipyard site. A glimpse of Sigtuna's maritime Middle Ages

By Rune Edberg ORCID 0009-0001-4070-5115

Introduction

Sigtuna is Sweden's oldest town within the country's medieval borders. Around the year 1000, king Olof Skötkonung had a manor house built there, along with establishing Sweden's first mint. The town was gradually divided into plots with housing, craftsmen and trading posts. Christian burial grounds were marked out around the settlement (Tesch 2008). The town is located on Lake Mälaren, surrounded by rural areas, fully colonized during the Iron Age.

A growing non-agricultural town population needed to be supplied with food, fuel and much more. Since people are people, then as now, one can use historical analogies to calculate the approximate quantities that were consumed. Every town dweller needed at least 1 kg of food a day and for heating, every household or workshop consumed at least 20 m³ of wood per year. Calculated on an assumed 500 inhabitants, this amounts to about 180 tons of foodstuff and for 50 buildings about 1,000 m³ of firewood (Edberg 2007 with sources cited there).

For example, if all the bulky wood was delivered to this shoreline town by water from the surrounding farms by smaller boats, with an average holding capacity of 2 m³, two boat calls per day were required during the sailing season to cover the town's yearly requirements of fuel alone. From the town back to the farms, the farmers may have shipped latrine, a desirable high-quality fertilizer, to spread on the fields. For the supposed 500 inhabitants, it can be calculated, also with the help of historical analogies, that 25 tons of this, in solid form, per year were produced (Dahlberg & Johansson 1941: 591pp.). Perhaps was wood ash from the town also used as fertilizer? Also, the town households certainly had their own boats for travel, fishing and other needs.

In other words, this early shipping on Lake Mälaren between the town and the surrounding countryside may have been intensive. And if you know where to look, you can still find traces today. Due to land uplift, Sigtuna's shoreline is now 4–5 m lower than it was 1,000 years ago. The reclaimed area has gradually been built up, thereby creating the conditions for a kind of underground marine archaeology.

Bulk finds

Excavations in the town began over a hundred years ago and Sigtuna Museum's archaeological collections are among the largest in Sweden. Gold and silver objects, various types of jewellery, amulets and much more of exotic origin, as well as over a hundred rune-carved objects, are among the most spectacular and notable finds. But the vast majority are of a more everyday nature. They are things that have been dropped or discarded and then trampled into the ground or used as fill. This mass material known archaeologically as bulk finds can include pot sherds and other broken items, bone-, antler- and metalworking waste, iron slag and burnt daub from fire-damaged houses.

The excavated find material includes vast amounts of scrapped iron artefacts, which at first glance may seem strange because in ancient times, iron objects required a lot of work in many different ways. They cannot have been cheap. Why was scrap left to rust away in the ground, which has been the case in Sigtuna since the town's earliest days? It is a fact that it was not until the 19th century that inventions made it possible to reuse scrap iron in iron production. Reforging broken nails, rivets and other small used iron objects on any large scale has never been practically feasible. The scrap iron was left where it fell, because it had become worthless.

Sigtuna's Viking Age and medieval occupational deposit layer covers approximately 10 ha with an estimated average thickness of 0.5 m, which corresponds to approximately 50,000 m³ of soil (recent excavations and similar interventions have not been taken into account). During the archaeological investigations in the town, an average figure of 1/3 kg of iron per m³ of soil examined has been recorded. This means just over 15 tons of archaeological iron. The wealth of finds also indirectly testifies to extensive iron production in the surrounding area, but this is another story. By comparison, there is an average figure of approximately 1/2 kg of pottery per m³ of soil. The amount of archaeological pottery, estimated in the same way, is approximately 25 tons.

Clench bolts with a meaning

As a research object, the sheer scope seems overwhelming or daunting. Strictly defined questions are therefore desirable more than ever. Even though one occasionally comes across distinguishable objects, the majority of the scrap iron consists of smaller or larger fragments, often fused together, with stones and other things, into shapeless lumps or conglomerates. But in Sigtuna there is after all a special category that can be distinguished and from which it turns out that meaningful knowledge can be obtained, namely clench bolts. The fact that discarded clench bolts have ended up in the ground is of course due to the fact that, like all other scrap iron, they have been unusable. But what does the very existence of this type of object on a large scale mean?

A clench bolt is a nail-like object – a rivet – with a large head at one end and a square or rhombic rove at the other (fig. 1). The joint is created by inserting the rivet into a pre-drilled hole in two overlapping pieces of wood. The rove is then pressed firmly on the opposite side and the rivet tip is snapped off and hammered over it. *After this process, the rivet and rove are no longer separate objects but parts of a new artefact: the clench bolt.* This is also illustrated by the fact that it is impossible to open a clench bolt without destroying it by knocking off the head, rove or stem (cf. Lundström 1973; see below about the find of a so-called nail finder). Although clench bolts have sometimes been used in certain carpentry works, it is in boats in the clinker-built tradition that they have occurred to a large extent. They are characteristic finds or key artifacts for boats and ships. Countless and well-known examples from all over Scandinavia illustrate this. Furthermore, the research terminology surrounding rivets and clench bolts in many languages is hopelessly confused, which greatly complicates comparisons (Edberg 2011a: 13–14; 2012; Zori 2007).

The preservation conditions for wooden timber in Sigtuna are generally poor. However, a small number of fragments of boat planks, with clench bolts fixed *in situ*, have nevertheless survived and been found archaeologically. Seven examples are from the 11th century, the town's oldest period (Fig. 2). Only one later find, from the second half of the 12th century, has been preserved, and that thanks to the surface wood being heavily scorched. The wood type is oak in all cases. A special case is the pieces of planking from a boat that was lying as a floor in a grave from the beginning of the 11th century. The wood had rotted away, but two rows of preserved clench bolts gave clues about how the boat had been built (Edberg 2011a; 2011b; 2012; 2023; Hed Jakobsson *et al.* 2017).

Unpreserved or wasted

While wooden boat parts with clenched bolts in their original position are thus rarely found in the occupation deposits, loose clenched bolts are found in very large quantities. Complete clenched bolts testify to boat wrecks or discarded parts of the planking. The internal dimensions of the clenched bolts show the dimensions of the planking. Cut rivets, as well as knocked-off rivet heads and roves, in turn tell of dismantling and repairs. They are highly visible traces of continuous shipyard activity in the town.

Archaeological iron is notoriously difficult to examine, especially since there is rarely any money for conservation. The decomposition then continues in the museum storeroom, where the iron slowly turns into rust powder. In addition, due to a lack of conservation budget, scrap iron is nowadays not recovered at all, but thrown away, which has also sometimes been the case in Sigtuna. The loss of source material is therefore very large for these various reasons, but despite everything, it has been shown that there are still quite a few objects that have retained their shape and structure to some extent and that can be studied.

In my research I have identified and examined over 1,000 clenched bolts from various sites in Sigtuna. Thanks to the fact that the large urban digs between 1998 and 2006 now have been analysed and published as reports, a large proportion of the finds can also be linked to context and time. Wooden material in the oldest layers in the Professorn 1 site was fairly well preserved and that site is the origin of six of the eight above-mentioned plank finds with clenched bolts (Wikström *et al.* 2021). The other two are from the Trädgårdsmästaren 9–10 site (Wikström 2011).

Measurable internal dimensions

I recently reviewed the iron recovered from the Professorn 1 site, and was able to identify 262 clenched bolts that were in such a condition that the internal dimensions could be measured with reasonable accuracy. The mean and median distance turned out to be 25 mm. The biggest number of clenched bolts were found in phase 8 of this excavation (1040–1055). There were also 127 loose roves, with or without remaining broken off rivet parts (fig. 3). They also had a peak in phase 8 with 25 specimens (fig. 4) (Edberg 2023).

The average clenched bolt size, 25 mm, from the Professorn 1 site can be compared with the corresponding ones from other find sites, which I have previously reviewed and published. It was completely consistent with the size from the Humlegården 3 site (with 95 studied specimens). However, it was slightly smaller than the equivalent in Trädgårdsmästaren 9–10 site (575 specimens) where the average size was 28 mm (Edberg 2011a, 2012, 2013).

In the Professorn 1 site, 55% of the clenched bolts date from before about 1100 (phases 1–11 of this excavation) and 30% from about 1100–1280 (phases 12–16). In the Trädgårdsmästaren 9–10 site, 30% of the clenched bolts date from before about 1100 (phases 1–5 of this excavation) while 67% date to about 1100–1270 (phases 6–10). Is the difference due to the fact that the clenched bolts from Trädgårdsmästaren 9–10 site have a later chronological focus? Did the boats generally become bigger over time? That would have been an appealing explanation, but the difference in dimensions between the two sites, albeit marginal, persists in all phases. A tendency towards the occurrence of larger boats can be suspected at the site near the shore, Professorn 4, where the 102 measurable specimens show an average of 31 mm. The stratigraphic dating here is relatively weak, but the vast majority of the objects can be dated to the 13th century or later (Edberg 2011a; 2012; 2014).

Moderately large boats

Despite some differences between the investigated sites, the inner distance of the clench bolts is everywhere, both on average and as a median, between 25 and 28 mm. This represents two boat planks one on top of another and correspond to a plank thickness of 12.5 to 14 mm. (Of course, in all boats in the clinker-built tradition there are both shorter clench bolts such as lacing rivets and longer ones such as frame top clench bolts, but in a general calculation these can be assumed to largely cancel each other out in length.) This measurement is, for example, in good agreement with the average clench bolt dimensions of the approximately 9 m long grave boats Valsgårde 12 and 15, from the second half of the 10th century, which were 25–26 mm (Virtanen 1983). The planks of the approximately 8 m long grave boat Valsgårde 1, from the first part of the 11th century, measured approximately 15 mm (Fridell 1930). An overview of the Valsgårde finds with examples can also be found in Larsson (2007: 89–90). It seems clear that boats of this size are seen in the Sigtuna find material. However, while the clench bolts provide a good indication of the size of the boats, it is not possible to make a statement based on them alone about the variation in boat types that may have existed.

When it comes to this kind of source material, archaeological reports do not often describe clench bolts found in detail, and when they do occur, the internal dimensions are rarely stated. Accurate comparisons between different sites are therefore out of the question. However, the fact that the planking used at about the same time, but elsewhere, in the construction of boats for Baltic shipping was stronger must be seen as scientific common knowledge. To take one example of many, the 22 m long Ladby boat was built with 20–25 mm thick planks (Thorvildsen 1959: 36). And to take another, the (at least) 16 m long boat in the chamber grave from Hedeby had about 25 mm thick planks (Müller-Wille 1976: 17–28). Incidentally, there is a parallel to the investigations in Sigtuna, precisely from Hedeby. A review of clench bolts from the site's cultural layer, nearly 700 specimens, showed an average size of 44 mm, corresponding to a plank thickness of 22 mm (Westphalen 2002: 203 ff.).

Boats for sale

The Sigtuna clench bolts date mainly from the end of the 10th century to the end of the 13th century. They are the remains of clinker-built boats of moderate size that continuously, century after century, were responsible for commercial traffic on Lake Mälaren. Of course, people both rowed and sailed: from the occupational deposits there are also finds of oars, oarlocks and mast parrels of the kind used in rigging square sails (Edberg 2011b; 2012; 2013).

The boats in traffic at Sigtuna were certainly built both on the farms in the surrounding countryside and in the town. But it is reasonable to assume that, analogous to the specialized craft, of which there are many archaeological examples of various kinds, there were also workshops that not only offered services for repairs and maintenance but also built boats to order and for sale to customers in the town and the surrounding countryside. Boats that can be assumed to have been at a higher technical level than the farmers' home-built boats. A typical tool, a crowbar-like so-called nail finder, is among the finds (fig. 5). To my knowledge, this type of tool was first brought to the attention of ship antiquarians by Per Lundström during the investigation of the Paviken site on Gotland. His opinion was that it could be used after the clench bolts had first been loosened with a chisel. Lundström demonstrated recent parallels (1973). Among the Sigtuna finds is also forged strips with roves, ready for use (fig. 6) (Cf. Edberg 2012; 2013.)

Two finds of anchors, one of which is very well preserved and previously published by me (Edberg 2011c), and a second, heavily rusted (fig.7) indicate that large ships also called at Sigtuna. The first can probably, the second fairly certainly, be stratigraphically placed in the 11th century. At this time, the anchor represented the highest level of blacksmithing, were great treasures and reserved for the finest ships of kings and noblemen. They are very rare as archaeological finds (Edberg 2007; 2011c; 2014). It is logical that Viking Age longships also appeared on Lake Mälaren. From rune stones we know that village chieftains equipped ships for foreign voyages and that Viking Age kings came to Sigtuna by sea is mentioned in royal sagas and bardic poetry. At the Battle of Svolder, in the year 1000, Olof Skötkonung participated with a large number of ships. There may also be traces of this type of ship among the clench bolts, although they have not been singled out with the general methodology applied so far.

Important shipyard

Is there any chance of finding boats and ships on the lakebed at Sigtuna? It certainly is, because in general there are wrecks from all times on the bottom of Lake Mälaren. Another reasonable assumption is that a harbour with greater depth and better shelter existed in a different place than just at the central town, where the landing place is unprotected from most wind directions. In other words, a place more suitable for such boats and ships that cannot simply be pulled up to the shore. Possible locations in the immediate vicinity of the town are, for example, at Munkholmen. A name for this place, noted in the 17th century, is Skeppsholmen ("Ship Islet"; Gihl 1925). Incidentally, a bathymetric survey carried out on behalf of the municipality by the company Marin Mätteknik has revealed several wrecks next to the bridge over Garnsviken, the former Tilesundet, just east of the town (Edberg 2012 with reference). This type of research, i.e. traditional "wet" marine archaeology, is still largely untested in Sigtuna.

Taken as a whole, archaeology shows how life in early Sigtuna was characterized by close interaction and connections between town and country through sea communication. It can be especially emphasized that the number of preserved clench bolts is very large and that this is evidence of large-scale boatbuilding, repairs and dismantling of boats in the clinker-built tradition. Sigtuna appears, also from a Scandinavian perspective, as an important shipyard site during the late Viking Age–early Middle Ages.

Finally, it can be pointed out that the bulk finds from Sigtuna and of course also from other similar sites where major investigations using modern stratigraphic methodology have been carried out, should be suitable for even more detailed investigations, preferably with the help of statistical methods.

References

Dahlberg, G. & I. Johansson (publ.) 1941. *Svenskt lantbrukslexikon*. Stockholm.

Edberg, R. 2007. Sigtunaleden och mysteriet med de saknade vikingaskeppen. *Situne Dei*, pp. 79–97.

Edberg, R. 2011a. *Vikingatida och tidigmedeltida båtar i Sigtuna. En undersökning baserad på fynd av nitförband i kulturlagren*. Meddelanden och rapporter från Sigtuna Museum, 50. Andra, reviderade upplagan.

Edberg, R. 2011b. Fynd. In: A. Wikström (ed.): *Fem stadsgårdar. Arkeologisk undersökning i kv. Trädgårdsmästaren 9 & 10 i Sigtuna 1988–90*. Meddelanden och rapporter från Sigtuna Museum, 52, pp. 141–174.

Edberg, R. 2011c. Ett vikingatida (?) ankare från Sigtuna. *Situne Dei*, pp. 66–73.

Edberg, R. 2012. Marinarkeologi under jorden. Aspekter på sjöfart, båtbygge och hamnförhållanden under vikingatid och tidig medeltid. *Situne Dei*. pp. 7–36.

- Edberg, R. 2013. Subterranean Maritime Archaeology in Sigtuna, Sweden: Excavated Evidence of Viking Age Boat Building and Repair. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* vol. 42–1, pp. 196–204.
- Edberg, R. 2014. *Sigtuna från sjösidan. Noteringar och kompletteringar från ett arkeologiskt projekt*. Meddelanden och rapporter från Sigtuna Museum, 57.
- Edberg, R. 2023. Nitar i tusental vittnar om det tidiga Sigtunas sjöfart. *Situne Dei*, pp. 52–59.
- Fridell, A. 1930. Den första båtgraven vid Valsgårde i Gamla Uppsala socken. *Fornvännen*, pp. 217–237.
- Hed Jakobsson, A., J. Runer, A. Kjellström & T. Björk. 2017. *I Sigtunas utkant. Slutundersökningsrapport över gravar och bebyggelse vid Götes mack*. Rapporter från Arkeologikonsult 2017: 2696.
- Gihl, G. 1925. *Sigtuna och Norrsunda. Tvenne antikvariskt-topografiska manuskript af Martinus Aschaneus, utgifna och kommenterade*. Uppsala.
- Müller-Wille, M. 1976. *Das Bootkammergrab von Haithabu*. Berichte über die Ausgrabungen in Haithabu, 8. Neumünster.
- Larsson, G. 2007. *Ship and Society. Maritime ideology in late iron age Sweden*. Uppsala.
- Lundström, P. 1973. Klinknaglarnas vittnesbörd. *Sjöhistorisk årsbok 1971–1972*, pp. 81–88.
- Tesch, S. 2008. Sigtuna ca 980–1200 – det maktpolitiska och sakrala stadsrummet. In: H. Andersson, G. Hansen & I. Øye (ed.). *De første 200 årene. Nytt blikk på 27 skandinaviske middelalderbyer*. Bergen, pp. 323–340.
- Thorvildsen, K. 1959. *Vikingskibet ved Ladby*. København.
- Westphalen, P. 2002. *Die Eisenfunde von Haithabu*. Die Ausgrabungen in Haithabu, 10. Neumünster.
- Wikström, A. (ed.). 2011. *Fem stadsgårdar. Arkeologisk undersökning i kv. Trädgårdsmästaren 9–10 i Sigtuna 1988–1990*. Meddelanden och rapporter från Sigtuna Museum, 52.
- Wikström, A., A. Söderberg & M. Roslund (ed.). 2021. *Hos herr Niklas och annat skrivkunnigt folk. Arkeologisk undersökning i kvarteret Professorn 1 i Sigtuna 1999–2000*. Meddelanden och rapporter från Sigtuna Museum, 63.
- Virtanen, H. 1983. *Båtnitar. En jämförande studie av några järnnitsfynd från kända och eventuella båtgravar*. Seminarieuppsats, Arkeologiska institutionen, Stockholms universitet.
- Zori, D. 2007. Nails, rivets, and clench bolts: A case for typological clarity. *Archaeologia Islandica* 6 (2007), pp. 3–47.

Figures, next page!

Figure 1. Suggested terms for rivet, rove and clench bolt in Swedish, English and German. From left: Nit (rivet, Niet) • Bricka, nitbricka (rove, Nietplatte) • Nitförband (clench bolt, Nietenverbindung).

Figure 2. Clench bolt in situ in oak boat planking. Professorn 1 site. c. AD 1040–1055. Photo Sigtuna Museum.

Figure 3. Some not stabilized clench bolts and roves from the Professorn 1 site, Sigtuna. Photo author.

Figure 5. "Cats' paw" from the S:t Gertrud 3 site, Sigtuna. Length 190 mm. 11th century. Tool, used to cut off clench bolts in boat repair work. Photo Sigtuna Museum.

Figure 6. Strip of roves, Professorn 4 site, Sigtuna. 13th century. In boat building and repair, the rove is forced on the rivet, constituting the clench bolt. Photo Sigtuna Museum.

Figure 7. An anchor, almost totally destroyed by rust, during excavation at the Professorn 4 site, Sigtuna, in 1996. 11th century. Length 110, Width 75 cm. Photo author.

Figure 4. From Sigtuna's Professorn 1 site, 262 clench bolts were measured. The average distance from the head's under side to the rove's top side was 25 mm.

Mätbara nitförband, kv. Professorn 1

